

Growth Saving Analysis, Credits, and Net Interest Margin to The Bank Risk in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

A bank risk is an uncertainty that can produce something undesirable, including in banking world. The existing deposits and credit can be the cause of risks emergence so it's needed to be well organized. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of deposit, credit and net interest margin (NIM) growth on bank risk that reflected through the measurement of risk on capital returns and standard deviation on assets (SDROA) as a measurement of risk on the growth asset. This study is a causal quantitative. The objects of the study are the banking sector listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2018-2021 period for about 45 banks with purposive sampling, so the population decided are 41 banks. The used analysis method is Eview 9. The results of the study show that deposit and credit growth affect the Standard Deviation of Return on Assets (SDROA), and Net Interest Margin (NIM) affects the Standard Deviation of Return on Equity (SDROE).

KEYWORDS: Growth of Deposit, Credit, Net Income Margin, Bank Risk.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic causes the changes of social order, especially due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the rapid development of information technology usage in recent years, resulting the changes of people's behavior and preferences in economic transactions. This drives the acceleration of digital transformation, including banking sector, that in 2022, banks massively strive to optimize the use of digital technology both in products and services to customers. In 2023, the trend projection is likely inseparable from digitalization aspect, including the masive adoption of digital technology, implementing hybrid banks, utilizing big data and customer experience, but other trends will still arise, (OJK, 2023).

The emergence of trends depends on consumers, because of their shifts in lifestyle causing the changes of individual behavior related environmental changes that occur. Changes of consumer behavior in banking must be observed

by banks in order to provide proper products and services that fit to consumers. Banking products and services cannot be separated from two main banking activities namely funding and lending.

Funding are bank activities to collect funds from public, later it is distributed through lending activities, such as credit/loan. Funding activities can be regular savings, deposits, time deposits, term deposits and checking deposits. (Martono, 2002) stated that depositor fund is also referred as third-party funds (TPF). Funding activities will be seen from deposit growth side, where the development of depositor funds can be seen from deposit growth side per year. The collected savings will be distributed through lending activities.

Lending is an activity of providing loans or credit to customers, this banks activity obtains returns of interest from loans given to customers. Lending activity in this study is seen from the growth credit side which is a comparison

between total credit in period t by total credit in previous period (t-1). Based on the data from Bank Indonesia’s surveys in the third quarter, there was a decrease of credit growth

compared to the previous year, (bi.go.id). The following graph was an increased and decreased of credit growth that occurred in the period 2018-2022:

Picture 1. The Graph of Credit Growth

Picture 2. The Graph of Third-Party Fund Growth

Based on picture 1, credit growth has decreased, this certainly should be analysed the indications that caused decrease in its growth, so it will be an evaluation of bank lending performance. The looseness or tightness of loans policies will certainly effect on existing risks, so the risk arise can be handled properly. Risk is something uncertain and it must be risky, especially in business world. In banking, risk is something cannot be avoided but is faced and managed properly, because risk is part of uncertainty, of course, anticipatory steps and efforts to minimize the risks must be taken by the bank. Based on picture 2, third-party funds growth has increased, this indicates that the funds collected by the bank are increasing and of course, this will increase the

bank’s capital. This cannot separated from the risks that arise because they are related to bank interest.

Several studies had examined factors could triggered bank risk such as Abdul-Rahman et al., 2018; Leung et al, 2015; Naili & Lahrichi, 2022, and other researchers. The results of the studies were diverse, but none had focused on the growth of credit deposits, and net interest margin (NIM), so a study on funding and lending activities that focus on both of growth side, that are deposits and credit is needed to be held.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Yakubu & Abokor, 2020 stated that in developing countries market, deposits are the core of bank activities. Beside deposits, many businesses are also assisted by business capital obtained from loans, so it does not only rely on capital from the company but also from the external, this also depends on financing preferences.

In financing, the role of deposits, mostly determine the amount of available funds are allocated for loan activities. Based on several result of the studies Abduh et al., 2011; Eriemo, 2014; Mushtaq & Siddiqui, 2017; Ojeaga et al, 2013 found mixed results of factors influence deposits, while the study conducted in Turkey Matur et al., 2012; Ozcan et al, 2003; Rijckeghem, 2010; Tatliyer, 2017 focused on determinants of people's savings behavior, but in their study less focused on how banks can increase their deposit growth as well as on savings growth.

Based on law number 10 in 1998, it states that savings are funds deposited by public to the banks, it can be checking accounts, savings, certificates of deposit, or other forms are similar (Law of the Republic of Indonesia, 1998). According to Martono, 2002 stated that public savings are also called third party funds. Thus, the banking sector must also think about how to attract the public to save their money, although on the other hand, it is a risky that in a bank the saving is in good growth, can caused the bank risk increase because of the the huge amount of funds resulted by public's trust, but if there is a massive withdrawal of savings, it will impact the bank risk. The risk must be managed properly so it does not have negative impact to the bank's performance. Thus, banks need to maintain their performance because it depends on how the bank's efforts to fulfill funding and lending activities properly and manage the arise risks, so the bank can manage strategy to mantain better savings growth, later it can be allocated for lending activities. Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H1a: Saving growth effect on SDROA

H1b: Saving growth effect on SDROE

Based on the study Rokhim 2020,found that the higher loan growth will aggravate credit risk, especially for Islamic banking, where it is not only enough from the capital, but also on the moral of endanger mitigation on loan risk must be treated carefully. The existing study also explains that credit growth has a significant impact on bank NPLs (non-performing loans), (Boudriga et al, 2010; Foos et al, 2010). This means that through credit growth can be one of causes of a financial crisis, especially that occurred recently, (Naili & Lahrichi, 2022).

Based on the results of conducted study, to support the increase of loan growth, banks will tend to relax loans,

hoping by applying this policy, it can encourage people to take out loans, by ignoring their eligibility of strict loan applications, but the facts by doing that will effect on the performance so this will cause the emergence of credit risk, if those happens on loans, it will impact on the increase of bad debts as well as on bank that losses on the credit growth. Based on these conditions, it can be hypothesized as follows:

H2a : Credit growth effect to SDROA

H2b : Credit growth effect to SDROE

Net interest margin (NIM) is one of the financial ratios usually used to measure the difference between the level of bank's interest income by the interest that must be paid on loans. It means that the difference between loan interest by bank's deposit interest rate. International Monetary Fund (IMF) states that the interest difference is the interest rate applied by banks to private sector customers reduced the interest rate paid by commercial banks/similar for a time deposit/savings deposit. In the study Barus & Lu, 2013 stated that the difference of bank interest rates is the main income used to determine the bank's net income. The higher income of interest obtained by the bank, as well as the increase of bank profitability, so the risk of bankruptcy will decrease. Based on the explanation above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H3a : Net interest margin (NIM) effects on SDROA

H3b : Net interest margin (NIM) effects on SDROE

METHODOLOGY

This study includes a causal quantitative study, to determine the effect of savings and credit growth on banking risk that observed from 2018-2021 in all banks listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). The total number of banks registered from 2018-2021 was 45 by applying purposive sampling, with the criteria of all banks that were active and complete in publishing financial reports during the observation, especially related to the financial data needed in this study. So, the samples were 41 banks that met these criteria.

The dependent variable in this study is banking risk which is proxied by standard deviation of return on equity (SDROE) and the standard deviation of return on assets (SDROA), while for the independent variables there are 2; growth deposits (X1), credit growth (X2), and net interest margin / NIM (X3). This used is multiple regression analysis with a panel data approach. The data obtained is processed using E-Views 9. SDROE is a comparison between profit before tax by the average of total equity in certain period. SDROE variable as a dependent variable is measured by the formula:

$$SDROE = \sqrt{\frac{(ROE_{it} - ROE_t)^2}{n - 1}}$$

While for standard deviation return on asset (SDROA) is a proxy on risk is used to measure on used asset, following is the formula:

$$SDROA = \sqrt{\frac{(ROA_{it} - ROA_t)^2}{n - 1}}$$

Savings growth is a comparison of difference between the amount of savings in a certain year by the amount of savings in previous year. The measurement uses the following formula:

$$\text{Growth Deposits} = \frac{\text{Total Deposit } t - \text{Total Deposit } t-1}{\text{Total Deposit}}$$

Credit growth is the total growth of credit given to third parties; the following formula is to measure it:

$$\text{Growth Credits} = \frac{\text{Total Loan } t - \text{Total Loan } t-1}{\text{Total Loan } t-1}$$

Net interest margin (NIM) is the difference between the loan interest rate by the bank's deposit interest rate. Here is the formula:

$$\text{NIM} = \frac{\text{Total Interest Income}}{\text{Average Total Earning Asset}} - \frac{\text{Total Interest Expense}}{\text{Average Total Interest - Earning Liabilities}}$$

Therefore, there are two models of equations that can be arranged as follows:

Model 1 $SDROE = \alpha + \beta_1GD + \beta_2GC + \beta_3NIM + e$

Model 2 $SDROA = \alpha + \beta_1GD + \beta_2GC + \beta_3NIM + e$

Where,

SDROE = Standard deviation ROE

SDROA = Standard deviation ROA

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficient with the equation of two models can be constructed as follows:

- regression of each variable, α = Constants
- GD = Growth deposits
- GC = Growth credits
- NIM = Net interest margin
- e = error

if it illustrated in a study model as follow:

Picture 3. Research Model

RESULTS

Based on the analysis, the results found that:

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis

	SDROE	SDROA	GD	GC	NIM
Mean	0,017	0,003	0,162	0,185	0,048
Median	0,008	0,001	0,110	0,059	0,043
Maximum	0,148	0,026	3,574	9,263	0,325
Minimum	0,000	0,000	-1,000	-0,907	-0,074
Std. Dev.	0,026	0,004	0,407	1,012	0,045
Skewness	3,351	3,516	4,793	7,089	3,191
Kurtosis	15,405	16,710	41,933	59,347	18,776
Jarque-Bera	1018,778	1216,808	8239,250	17301,840	1484,319
Probability	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000

Sum	2,117	0,348	19,971	22,767	5,890
Sum Sq. Dev.	0,081	0,002	20,226	124,883	0,245
Observations	123	123	123	123	123

Based on the table above, there are 123 observations, for standard deviation return on equity has average 0,017, the standard deviation return on asset is 0,003, growth deposit 0,162, growth credit 0, 185, and net interest income is 0,048. While for median of standard deviation equity is 0, 008, standard and standard deviation return on asset is 0,001, growth deposit 0,110, growth credit 0, 059, also net interest

income by 0,043. Whereas the maximum point of standard deviation returns on equity by 0, 148, standard deviation returns on asset 0,026, growth deposit 3,574, growth credit by 9, 263, and net interest income 0,325, while for minimum point equity by 0, 000, standard deviation returns on asset 0,000, growth deposit -1,000, growth credit by -0, 907, dan net interest income by -0,074.

THE RESULT OF PANEL DATA REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Based on the analysis of data panel regression resulted 3 models as follows:

Table 2 Common Effect Model

Dependent Variable: SDROA

Method: PLS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0,003303	0,000581	5,689025	0
GD	-0,00037	0,001059	-0,34539	0,7304
GC	0,000245	0,000425	0,576918	0,5651
NIM	-0,00963	0,00883	-1,09088	0,2775

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Table 3 Fixed Effect Model

Dependent Variable: SDROA

Method: PLS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0,003957	0,001313	3,014735	0,0035
GD	-0,0029	0,001149	-2,52142	0,0137
GC	-0,00039	0,000451	-0,86686	0,3886
NIM	-0,01224	0,027142	-0,45107	0,6532

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Table 4 Random Effect Model

Dependent Variable: SDROA

Method: PLS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0,003402	0,000593	5,732814	0
GD	-0,00089	0,000969	-0,9187	0,3601
GC	0,000113	0,000387	0,291811	0,7709
NIM	-0,0094	0,008996	-1,04526	0,298

Source: Data processing by Eviews (202)

Table 5 Common Effect Model

Dependent Variable: SDROE

Method: PLS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0,021143	0,003464	6,10314	0
GD	-0,00176	0,006315	-0,2793	0,7805
GC	-0,00044	0,002534	-0,17477	0,8616
NIM	-0,07436	0,052682	-1,41141	0,1607

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Table 6 Fixed Effect Model

Dependent Variable: SDROE

Method: PLS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0,025261	0,008352	3,024585	0,0034
GD	-0,01096	0,007311	-1,49967	0,1377
GC	-0,00245	0,002867	-0,85331	0,3961
NIM	-0,12141	0,172708	-0,70297	0,4841

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Table 7 Random Effect Model

Dependent Variable: SDROE

Method: PLS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0,021537	0,003741	5,757534	0
GD	-0,00362	0,00615	-0,58814	0,5576
GC	-0,00085	0,002458	-0,34419	0,7313
NIM	-0,07473	0,056722	-1,31753	0,1902

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Estimation Selection Techniques of Panel Data Regression

Chow Test (Significant Test Fixed Effect Model)

Table 8 Chow Test

Dependent Variable: SDROA

Method: PLS

Effect Test	Statistic	d.f	Prob.
Cross Section F	1,989	(40,79)	0,0047

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Based on Chow Test above the probability values is $0,0047 < 0,005$ so the best model is **fixed effect model (FEM)**.

Table 9 Chow Test

Dependent Variable: SDROE

Method: PLS

Effect Test	Statistic	d.f	Prob.
Cross Section F	1,510	(40,79)	0,06

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Based on Chow Test above the probability values is $0,06 > 0,05$ so the best model is **common effect model (CEM)**.

Hausman Test

Table 10 Hausman Test of SDROA

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: REM

Dependent Variable: SDROA

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f	Prob.
Cross-section random	21.157	3	0.001

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Based on table above probability values is $0,001 < 0,05$ so the best model is **fixed effect model (FEM)**.

Table 11 Hausman Test of SDROE

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: REM

Dependent Variable: SDROE

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.894	3	0.075

Source: Data processing by Eviews (2023)

Based on the table above, the probability value is $0.075 > 0.05$ so that the best model is Random Effect Model (REM). Based on the Chow test and Hausman test, it can be concluded that for SDROA the best model is Fixed Effect Model (FEM), while for SDROE the best model is Random Effect Model (REM). The classical assumption test for normality is met, while for multicollinearity there are no symptoms, and heteroscedasticity is free from symptoms, including free autocorrelation. Based on the output, so the arranged equations from the two models are as follows:

$$\text{Model 1 SDROA} = 0,0033 - 0,0017*GD + 0,0003*GC - 0,0067*NIM + e$$

$$\text{Model 2 SDROE} = 0,0225 - 0,0041*GD + 0,0018*GC - 0,1030*NIM + e$$

DISCUSSION

Based on the conducted analysis, it can be concluded that the accepted hypothesis is in H1a, H2a, and H3b accepted while for H1b, H2b, and H3a are rejected. While for H1a, deposit growth affects risk in a negative direction through the measurement of standard deviation return on assets (SDROA), this occurred if the deposit growth is getting increase, and affect the bank's risk will decrease, this happens because the better deposit growth, causes the bank's capital is getting bigger, as well as the lending activities or loans given to community. In the other word if there is a problems related loans on community, it will not be at great risk because of the capital bank's asset is already bigger.

H2a credit growth affects bank risk through the measurement of standard deviation return on assets (SDROA), with a positive direction, meaning that the greater credit growth, as well as the bank's risk of return on assets side. This means that the higher credit growth, as well as the opportunity to gain income from the interest side, but this will also be followed by a higher level of risk, so banks need to supervise the possible arise risks in order to be able to minimize a negative impact on the bank.

H3b Net Interest Income (NIM) affects the risk measured through the standard deviation of return on equity (SDROE) in a negative direction. This happens when NIM is higher, so the bank's risk through the standard deviation of return on equity will decrease. This because of the net interest income is gained higher minus all existing expenses, so it will

increase the bank's equity/capital, by sufficient capital, the bank's risk will be lower, considering net income is getting higher as well as the bank capital, it can be re-allocated through lending activities to the community.

CONCLUSION

Based on the existing hypothesis, H1a is accepted, because with the growth of deposits getting better, the bank's capital is getting larger, which has an impact on the increase in bank assets that can be used for lending activities to the community. H2a, accepted because credit growth is higher, the opportunity for income in terms of interest, will be greater level of risk. H3b is acceptable, because the higher the net interest income will increase the bank's capital, so the larger the capital, the lower the bank's risk.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study has limitations on model, where the factors that can affect bank risk are not only on deposit growth variables, credit growth, and net interest income, but also there are many other variables that can affect bank risk, or by involving mediation or moderation variables as variables that can be an intermediaries/strengthening/weakening the relationship between independent variables and bank risk (dependent variables). By these limitations, it is expected that there will be another study with different development related to bank risk.

REFERENCES

1. Abdul-Rahman, A., Sulaiman, A. A., & Said, N. L. H. M. (2017). Does Financing Structure Affect Bank Liquidity Risk? Pacific-Basin Finance Journal.
2. Bahçeci, S. (2012). Determinants of private saving and interaction between public & private savings in Turkey. Topics in Middle Eastern and North African Economies, 14.
3. Barus, A. C., & Lu, M. (2013). The influence of interest rate spread and financial ratios on the distribution of MSME credit at general banks in Indonesia. Jurnal Wira Ekonomi Mikroskil, 3(1), 11-20.
4. Boudriga, A., Taktak, N. B., & Jellouli, S. (2010). Problem loans in the MENA countries: bank specific

determinants and the role of business and institutional environment. In *The Economic Study Forum: Working Papers no* (Vol. 547).

5. Foos, D., Norden, L., & Weber, M. (2010). Loan growth and riskiness of banks. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 34(12), 2929-2940.
6. Leung, W. S., Taylor, N., & Evans, K. P. (2015). The determinants of bank risks: Evidence from the recent financial crisis. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 34, 277-293.
7. Martono. (2002). *Bank and other Financial Institution* (1st ed.). Yogyakarta: Ekonisia.
8. Matur, E. P., Sabuncu, A., & Bahçeci, S. (2012). Determinants of private saving and interaction between public & private savings in Turkey. *Topics in Middle Eastern and North African Economies*, 14.
9. Naili, M., & Lahrichi, Y. (2022). The determinants of banks' credit risk: Review of the literature and future study agenda. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 27(1), 334-360.
10. Nguyen, J. (2012). The relationship between net interest margin and noninterest income using a system estimation approach. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 36(9), 2429-2437.
11. Ozcan, K. M., Gunay, A., & Ertac, S. (2003). Determinants of private savings behaviour in Turkey. *Applied Economics*, 35(12), 1405-1416.
12. Rokhim, N., Wahdi, N., & Santoso, A. (2020). Examining the Determinants of Company Value. *BBM (Buletin Bisnis & Manajemen)*, 6(2), 78-87.
13. Tatliyer, M. (2017). Determinants of private saving level: Evidence from Turkey. *Sosyoekonomi*, 25(32), 149-167.
14. Van Rijckeghem, C. (2010). Determinants of private saving in Turkey: An update. *Boğaziçi Üniversitesi İktisat Bölümü Çalışma Tebliği*, 4, 1-97.
15. Yakubu, I. N., & Abokor, A. H. (2020). Factors determining bank deposit growth in Turkey: an empirical analysis. *Rajagiri management journal*, 14(2), 121-132.